

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THERENCE NWANA****FIRST NAME: DINGANA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 10%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following statements concerning academic essay writing is CORRECT?

- The introduction moves from specific to general.
- The conclusion moves from specific to general.¹**
- The conclusion is a paraphrased introduction.
- It is a good practice to introduce new information or ideas in the conclusion.

2. Which of the following is not a good essay writing habit?

- Starting early.
- Trying to write your essay from beginning to end in one session.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

² Ibid., 11.

- Writing the introduction and conclusion after writing the body.
 - Revising your first draft extensively.
3. Qualities of a good abstract include the following EXCEPT;
- It should be a concise summary of the study.
 - It should be limited to 350 words.
 - It should include the problem, purpose, scope, data sources, and findings.
 - The methodology should be excluded.**³
4. Which of the following is the right ordering of the content of a dissertation?
- 1. Introduction 2. Literature review 3. Methodology 4. Findings 5. Analysis and Interpretation 6. Conclusions and recommendations.**⁴
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 - 1. Introduction 2. Methodology 3. Findings. 4 Analysis and Interpretation 5. Literature review 6. Conclusions and recommendations.
5. Which of the following does NOT constitute plagiarism?
- Writing another person's idea, opinion, or theory without referencing.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th Edition. (Sage, Los Angeles, CA, 2018), 68.

⁴ Ibid., 73.

- Stating common facts without referencing.**⁵
- Quoting another person's actual spoken or written words without referencing.
- Carefully paraphrasing another person's spoken or written words without referencing.
6. A good recommendation should have the following qualities EXCEPT;
- It should be logically and clearly derived from your findings and those of similar studies.**⁶
- It should be both content and context specific, and most important.
- It should be practical; that is, it is capable of implementation.
- It should have implications for policy and practice, as well as for further research.
7. The following qualities make the source of your information reliable, EXCEPT?
- If the source is published by a reputable press.
- If the book or article is peer-reviewed.
- If the author is a reputable scholar.
- If the source is available online, irrespective of the sponsor.**⁷
8. Which of the following Turabian author-date citations is wrong?

⁵ Ibid., 222.

⁶ Ibid., 680.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago style for students and researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42.

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9. Which of the following is NOT a measure of quality in academic essay writing?

- Build coherence by connecting sentences.
- Organize your thoughts in a coherent, well-constructed paragraph.
- Make use of headings and subheadings to provide structure to your writing.
- Use specialized terms and jargon to make your work unique.⁹

10. The following are advantages of WHO house style, EXCEPT;

- It gives WHO information products a consistent and professional appearance and increases WHO’s credibility.
- It presents a single, cohesive image to readers.

⁸ Ibid., 332.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 213.

- It streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process by WHO staff.
- Freelance writers and editors pay to learn the WHO house style, and this generates income.¹⁰**

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO style guide*, 2nd edition. (Geneva: WHO Press, 2013), 1.

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